

Machine Learning Models for Vessel Route Forecasting: An Experimental Comparison

Eva Chondrodima
Dept. of Informatics
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
evachon@unipi.gr

Petros Mandalis
Dept. of Statistics and Ins. Sci.
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
pmandalis@unipi.gr

Nikos Pelekis
Dept. of Statistics and Ins. Sci.
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
npelekis@unipi.gr

Yannis Theodoridis
Dept. of Informatics
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
ytheod@unipi.gr

Abstract—Maritime transport systems are essential to human mobility. A vital part of the maritime transport systems is the accurate vessel route forecasting (VRF). However, accurate VRF is a challenging task due to the fact that maritime traffic conditions are complex and dynamic. Machine learning (ML) methods can leverage from the “explosion” of vessel surveillance information in order to encourage, enable deeper digitalization in the shipping industries and tackle the VRF problem. In this paper we investigate some of the most popular ML methods to address the VRF problem and we present an overview of these methods through an experimental testbed based on real vessel surveillance data. This work results in introducing baseline ML models for VRF purposes.

Index Terms—Machine Learning, Maritime data, Route Prediction, Trajectory Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime transport systems (MTS) are vital for global, European and National security, finance and trade. Thus, the shipping industry investments continue to grow in order to improve MTS, to better monitor and understand maritime transport and vessel traffic. The growing number of ship sensing technologies, such as the Automatic identification system (AIS), which is a self-reporting system that allows vessels to broadcast their identification and voyage-related information, is providing a wealth of vessel positioning data well-suited to be used in a wide range of applications [1].

Vessels’ mobility forecasting is an important part of MTS. Particularly, there is a growing interest regarding the vessel route forecasting (VRF) problem, in other words, the prediction of the anticipated locations of a moving object taking into account its own or the population’s motion history [2]. In this paper, the informal version of the VRF problem that we address is as follows: Given an irregular trajectory of a vessel consisting of past timestamped locations, a look-ahead prediction horizon and a look-ahead number of transitions, the goal is to predict the anticipated future trajectory of length equal to the given look-ahead number of transitions at a fixed sampling rate and up to the given look-ahead prediction horizon.

Accurate VRF can assist shipping industry in improving travel efficiency, while it has a wide range of applications, such as forecasting collisions, traffic jams, etc. Accurate VRF

is a challenging task due to a variety of factors, including stochastic variables such as weather conditions, etc.

Machine learning (ML) methods can leverage from the “explosion” of vessel surveillance information in order to encourage, enable deeper digitalization in the shipping industries and tackle the VRF problem more accurately. Currently, a limited number of maritime monitoring systems employ ML technology [3] [4]. Moving from traditional to ML solutions in the maritime domain is a challenging task, while generally it is not easy to bring the core technology into practice. In the literature, there are several works, which tackle the route forecasting problem either on the maritime field [5]–[11] or other domains [12]–[15] and are presented in the following section. However, most of these works present a limited comparison analysis among them, thus making hard to evaluate the required robustness of the various alternatives, towards operational usage in the MTS.

Also, due to the variable sampling rate that characterizes the vessel surveillance data, most of the abovementioned works use downsampling methods or they resample the entire dataset by employing preprocessing techniques such as interpolation methods to create points of a constant sampling rate. As pointed out in [2], the assumption of interpolation in-between two consecutive sampled points is very common in order to simulate the continuous movement of objects, whereas linear interpolation is the most popular method followed. ML methods fail to model the temporal irregularity and in order to handle time series data, often, make strong assumptions on the data generation process (such as using interpolation methods), which can lead to poor model predictions [16].

Different from these works, we tackle the vessel surveillance data variable sampling rate problem by feeding the ML models with time and spatial information in the form of differences with regards to previous values. The use of differences enhances the NN models for handling irregular time series data [16], [17].

In summary, the main contribution of this work is to examine the most popular ML methods in order to address the VRF problem and to provide comparison results based on real AIS data. This work could be used as a reference for MTS to comprehend the most popular ML methods and facilitate their realization inside operational MTS.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses related work; Section III formulates the problem at hand, presents the proposed preprocessing method for VRF purposes, and briefly summarizes popular ML solutions; Section IV describes the available AIS data, presents the experimental setup and the experimental findings, and compares the performance of different solutions; Section V concludes the paper and discusses future extensions.

II. RELATED WORK

Xiao et.al. [18] provided a systematic review of the latest progress on maritime traffic forecasting technologies. The fact that the route or trajectory forecasting problem has been extensively studied brings up its importance and applicability in a wide range of applications. These works are mostly ML methods and can be categorized in two main types.

One line of work includes clustering-based prediction techniques. Petrou et.al. [14] employed on subtrajectory clustering [19] in order to be able to extract individual subtrajectory patterns from big mobility data. Subtrajectory clustering [19] considers linear interpolation between successive sampled points and produces patterns that can be utilized to predict the future location of the moving objects in parallel. Also, Pallotta et.al. [20] employed the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck mean-reverting stochastic technique combined with the TREAD [21] method to predict vessel movement; TREAD is an unsupervised-incremental learning approach, which is based on DBSCAN algorithm to detect low-likelihood behaviors.

A different way of addressing the route/trajectory forecast problem includes predictive analytics methods. As far as the maritime domain is concerned, Tu et al. [5] proposed Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) models to learn various vessel motion patterns by using all the available side information from AIS data. The proposed method performs multiple time prediction for four different length up to 60 min, while the error ranges from 1 n.m. to 4 n.m.

A single layer NN was also proposed by Zorbas et.al. [7] where a fixed time window NN model transforms the input in sets of consecutive vessel positions to predict the next position up to 60 min; reported results include the mean error, which ranges from 3 km for 30 min. predictions, to 7 km for 60 min. predictions. Taking advantage of [7], Valsamis [8] employed NNs to predict the positions of vessels by using different datasets with fixed prediction intervals.

In the literature, in the maritime domain, there are also focusing in works that leverage from Neural Network (NN) and particularly from Recurrent NN (RNN) [22]. RNNs constitute a popular method for trajectory prediction due to their powerful ability to fit complex functions, along with their ability of adjusting the dynamic behaviour as well as capturing the causality relationships across sequences. In order to predict the movement trend of vessels in the crowded port water of Tianjin port, Wang et.al. [9] proposed a vessel berthing trajectory prediction model based on bidirectional RNN-based networks and cubic spline interpolation. Capobianco et.al. [10] provided a genuine DL approach for vessel trajectory prediction. Their

contributions include the extraction of trajectories from AIS data, given a time-window and an area of interest and an RNN-based encoder-decoder using the attention mechanism to predict the vessel trajectories architecture. Suo et.al. [11] presented an RNN-based model to predict vessel trajectories based on a) the DBSCAN clustering algorithm to derive main trajectories and b) a symmetric segmented-path distance approach to eliminate the influence of a large number of redundant data and to optimize incoming trajectories. Ground truth data from AIS in the port of Zhangzhou, China, were used to train and verify the validity of the proposed model.

Most of the above works have not been cross-validated in comparison to each other and this is mandatory for the industry. In this paper, we examine the most popular ML methods in different vessel motion patterns and identify the most accurate ones for VRF purposes.

III. MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR VESSEL ROUTE FORECASTING

This section introduces the problem formulation, presents the proposed AIS preprocessing procedure, and briefly summarizes typical solutions for VRF purposes. Also, it describes the input-output data according to the problem formulation.

A. Problem Formulation

Consider a maritime dataset D composed of vessel trajectories and each trajectory is a tuple $\langle o-id, S \rangle$, where $o-id$ is the vessel's unique identifier and S is a sequence of timestamped locations (p_i, t_i) . No assumption is made about the sampling rate, i.e., $|t_{i+1} - t_i| \neq |t_i - t_{i-1}|$ in the general case.

Using D (for training purposes), the VRF problem addressed in this paper is formulated as follows:

- **Given:** (i) an active trajectory $T_a = \langle o-id, S_a \rangle$ where $S_a = \langle (p_1, t_1), (p_2, t_2), \dots, (p_k, t_k) \rangle$, (ii) a time duration (prediction horizon) Δt , and (iii) a number of transitions r ,
- **Predict:** the vessel's future trajectory (up to Δt) sequence of locations S'_a in r transitions equally distanced in time, i.e., $S' = \langle (p_{k+1}, t_{k+1}), (p_{k+2}, t_{k+2}), \dots, (p_{k+r}, t_{k+r}) \rangle$, where $|t_{k+1} - t_k| = |t_{k+2} - t_{k+1}| = \dots = |t_{k+r} - t_{k+r-1}| = \Delta t/r$.

B. AIS data preprocessing procedure

Due to transceiver errors AIS records contain faulty data [8]; therefore we apply typical data cleansing operations to the available AIS data, including record deduplication, noise elimination (by removing records corresponding to speed higher than 50 knots), and stationary simplification (by removing records corresponding to speed less than 1 knot). Although it may sound optional, the latter is a critical cleansing process in order for the ML model to avoid considering non-evolving parts of the trajectories. Furthermore, we did not consider vessels that turned out to have a very low number of points. In fact, we set 10 to be the minimum number of points of a trajectory of a vessel.

As already discussed, in the literature, the AIS variable sampling rate issue is often addressed by transforming variable to fixed time steps. However, this leads to higher computational load and in some cases to poor precision. Thus, in this paper, instead of employing the actual AIS values, we use the differences in time and space between consecutive time-stamped positions. Particularly, the time difference between k and $k-1$ entries in the trajectory of a vessel can be calculated as: $\Delta t_k = t_k - t_{k-1}$. Similarly, the intervals of Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) system easting and northing are calculated by $\Delta x_k = x_k - x_{k-1}$ and $\Delta y_k = y_k - y_{k-1}$, respectively.

Furthermore, vessel trajectories, derived from AIS, are sparse. In order to produce meaningful trajectory information, in this paper, original trajectories are segmented into a number of sub-trajectories when the time interval between two consecutive points of the same trajectory exceeds a specific threshold, equal to 30 min. (this also defines the maximum prediction time interval). For technical reasons, the resulted trajectories are further segmented into a number of sub-trajectories when the length of the trajectory exceeds a specific threshold, equal to 1000 points.

Finally, we transform the processed data into a supervised learning problem. The sequence of the broadcasted spatiotemporal information defining vessels' movements formulate the vessels' trajectories, which can be considered as spatial time series [7]. Time series related problems can be transformed to supervised problems by using the sliding window method [23]. A sliding window method maps an input window of length l into an output value; the window-length l is based on the ML-method type.

C. Machine learning methods

As a performance baseline, various ML methods were employed in this study to address the VRF problem. As a first step, a linear regression model [24] was employed. Also, as a representative of kernel based algorithms we employed Support Vector Machine for regression (SVMr) [25], [26], a counterpart of Support Vector Machine (SVM) [27] for solving regression problems.

Considering tree-based methods, a classic Classification and Regression Tree (CART) algorithm [28] was employed. Focusing on Ensemble of trees techniques [29], we employed Bagging and Boosting algorithms [30], [31]. More specifically, considering algorithms of Ensemble of Trees using Bagging we selected Random Forests Trees (RFT) [31], while for the Boosting category we selected Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) method [32].

NNs [33] constitute one of the most powerful families of techniques in the ML arsenal. In this paper, both static and dynamic networks [34] were employed. More specifically, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) was used with topologies of two hidden neurons and it was trained with the classic Back-propagation algorithm [33], whereas considering the dynamic NNs category we employed two RNN [22] extended architectures, the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [35]

and the Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) [36]. The RNN-based architectures were composed of an input layer of four neurons, an RNN-based hidden layer, a fully-connected hidden layer and an output layer of two neurons. Two alternative RNN-based hidden layers, GRU and LSTM were used. Details for the Backward Propagation Through Time (BPTT) algorithm, which was employed for updating the network parameters, can be found in [37]. Also, the synaptic weights were optimized according to the Adam methodology [38] on the training set.

D. Model Input-Output

Different ML techniques as well as different NN architectures enable different data representations to be learned [39]. All the abovementioned ML algorithms, except RNN-based models, can be applied immediately on data without time dependency, because they simply map input to output and do not consider the previous steps. More specifically, they consider all features to be independently, which do not apply in sequential -based problems [40].

In the case of time series related problems, the sequential information is necessary to be included through a set of delays that are added to the input, so that the data are represented at different points in time. The information relevant for making predictions need to be within a window of a number of past observations [41]. Particularly, the model input composed of the vessel's k' -th trajectory can be described by the following equation:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k'} = [(\Delta x_{k'-l}, \Delta y_{k'-l}, \Delta t_{k'-l}), \dots, (\Delta x_{k'-1}, \Delta y_{k'-1}, \Delta t_{k'-1}), (\Delta x_{k'}, \Delta y_{k'}, \Delta t_{k'}), \Delta t_{k'+r'}] \quad (1)$$

where l is the number of past observations - trajectory's points (i.e., the window size) and r' denotes the r' -th future transition.

The corresponding model output of the r' -th future transition can be described by the following equation:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_{k'} = (\Delta x_{k'+r'}, \Delta y_{k'+r'}) \quad (2)$$

We consider VRF problem as a means of a temporal multi-point location forecasting process. Thus, $\Delta t_{k'+r'}$ denotes the prediction time horizon of one point in the future. Taking into account the problem formulation described in Section III-A, the trained model need to be executed r times, in order to give predictions for the r transitions that formulate the predicted trajectory, i.e., the model output is the following:

$$[\Delta \mathbf{p}_{k'+1}, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{p}_{k'+r}] = [(\Delta x_{k'+1}, \Delta y_{k'+1}), \dots, (\Delta x_{k'+r}, \Delta y_{k'+r})] \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, the model output is transformed from differences to actual values and as a result the final model output is described by Eq. 4:

$$[\mathbf{p}_{k'+1}, \dots, \mathbf{p}_{k'+r}] = [(x_{k'+1}, y_{k'+1}), \dots, (x_{k'+r}, y_{k'+r})] \quad (4)$$

The optimal window size l is an important parameter, as the traditional ML methods (except RNN-based architectures)

Fig. 1. Overview of the employed datasets: (a) Aegean-Cyclades, (b) Brest

can only model the data within the input window. More specifically, a small window may not provide the necessary information to the model to learn and a too large window may not be well handled by the model, i.e., the method may be unsuited for too long-term dependencies. For instance MLPs overfit on the training data when using large windows [42].

On the other hand, RNN-based architectures have the capability to dynamically incorporate past experience due to internal recurrence. Hence, if the model output of the r' -th future transition is described by Eq. 2, then the model input can be described by the following equation:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k'} = [(\Delta x_{k'}, \Delta y_{k'}, \Delta t_{k'}), \Delta t_{k'+r'}] \quad (5)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

This section presents the experimental setup and the experimental findings, along with the evaluation of the effectiveness of the employed models.

A. Datasets, description and preparation

In order to evaluate the implemented models on different motion patterns we performed our experiments on real-world AIS data collected from two different sea areas. Data-driven techniques require massive amounts of data for learning purposes. In the literature, the employed datasets for VRF purposes using ML models, often, include records obtained from vessels during one month period [5], [8]. Particularly, in [8] the selected dataset contained 1,315,474 AIS records from 2874 vessels of different types whereas in [5] the selected dataset contained 403,599 AIS records from 180 vessels of different types. Based on these statistics, the employed datasets in this paper can be considered to be sufficient for VRF purposes. A description of the two employed datasets is given in the following paragraphs.

1) *Aegean-Cyclades Dataset*: The dataset provided by MarineTraffic.com includes a total of 1,720,368 records of location related information derived from AIS messages of vessels sailing in the Aegean Sea, Greece, during November,

2018. In detail, it corresponds to AIS activity transmitted by 2645 distinct vessels of various types and covers an area in the Aegean Sea that falls in the rectangle bounded by latitude in [36.2 ... 38.0] and longitude in [23.2 ... 25.8], as illustrated in Fig.1a. This spatial window was selected in order to evaluate the implemented algorithms in more complicated trajectories since it includes mixed activities, from cruise and passenger ships to fishing boats. Particularly, this spatial window includes vessel trips among several Greek ports, such as Piraeus, Santorini, Serifos, Milos, Sifnos, Paros, Syros, Naxos, Ios, Hydra, etc. As already discussed, vessels broadcast original position reports at varying time intervals, depending on their speed and the type of their AIS transponder. In this dataset, the sampling rate (before the pre-processing stage) varied from less than 1 sec. to several days, with a mean (median) value about 20 min. (2.5 min., respectively). Also, there exist vessels that transmit only a few signals (e.g. 1 or 2 signals in the entire 1-month period) and others that transmit a very large number of signals in the period of interest (12764 being the maximum number of signals recorded by a unique vessel, with a median value about 345 signals). These findings argue that pre-processing is an essential step for ML purposes; as such, the dataset was preprocessed as was described in Section III-B. Particularly, after conducting the cleansing procedure we perform trajectory segmentation, using the threshold maximum time interval between two consecutive points equal to 30 min. The resulting dataset is composed of a total of 1,156,879 records, 8139 trajectories and 2344 distinct vessels, with the trajectory length ranging from 10 to 975 points.

2) *Brest Dataset*: The employed dataset provided by [43] includes a total of 18,657,858 AIS records of location related information collected by the AIS receiver located in Brest, France, from October 1, 2015 to March 31, 2016. The AIS activity was transmitted by 5041 distinct vessels of various types covering a sea area that falls in the rectangle bounded by latitude in [-10.0 ... 0.0] and longitude in [45.0 ... 51.0], as illustrated in Fig.1b. More information about the original

dataset can be found in [43]. After combining the available dynamic and static information [43], removing the invalid MMSI [44], and preprocessing the data as was described in Section III, the resulting dataset was composed of a total of 6,038,793 records, 20455 trajectories and 1477 distinct vessels, with the trajectory length ranging from 10 to 1000 points.

B. Experimental protocol - Model parameter selection

The processed data were organised into input-output data according to Section III-D. Afterwards, a method evaluation procedure, similar to [45] was adopted, where the available trajectories were allocated randomly into three sets: training, validation and testing, employing 50%–25%–25% ratio, respectively. Obviously, the three sets include different trajectories of the available vessels, i.e., data of the training set cannot be found in the validation or testing set.

For all the implemented models, parameters were determined using the training set and then model selection was performed using the validation set. The selected model's performance was tested on the testing set, which is independent of training and model selection and thus can assess generalization capabilities.

Regarding model parameterization, several aspects of each model type were taken into account and optimized with intermediate experiments before the final performance assessment, with the exception of linear regression, which is essentially non-parametric. As far as the SVMr method is concerned, it was employed with Gaussian kernel function. Also, an exhaustive search procedure based on grid search adopted for optimizing the width of the Gaussian kernels γ and the penalty factor C .

Considering the tree-based algorithms, the CART models were optimized with respect to the minimum leaf size for pruning and the maximum number of features randomly selected on a node, which affects the number of leaves and the depth of the tree. The same parameters were used for optimizing the RFT models along with the number of regression trees in the ensemble. The same parameters, as in the case of RFT, were used for optimizing the AdaBoost method along with the learning rate that defines the contribution of each model to the ensemble prediction.

Moreover, the parameter selection of the employed NN-based architectures was based on theoretical aspect, as well as experimentation. An early stopping procedure [46] was used to prevent all the NN networks from overfitting by using a validation set. Typically the NN training phase is followed by a validation phase and eventually model selection [47]. A large number of epochs could lead to overfitting, i.e., the NN predicts poorly on data that have not been used in the training phase. The use of validation set results in measuring the generalization ability of the model. To this end, the NN that performs better for a given number of epochs in the validation set is finally selected; in other words, training stops when the error does not reduce for a given number of epochs in the validation set.

C. Results and Discussion

In route/trajectory prediction, the model performance is usually assessed with the use of the two following metrics for computing prediction error [48], [49]:

- Average displacement error (ADE): the average distance error over all the predicted positions in the predicted trajectory and the corresponding points in the ground truth trajectory for all predicted time steps.
- Final displacement error (FDE): the distance error between the predicted position and the true point in the final destination, i.e., in the trajectory's last point.

Table I depicts the results in terms of ADE (in meters) for a vessel's future trajectory up to Δt equal to 30 min. and r equal to 6 transitions, which results in a 5 min. sampling rate. Also, Table I depicts the results in terms of FDE (in meters) for vessel's future trajectory for Δt equal to 30 min. Results clearly show that the RNN-based methods outperform the static methods in terms of both ADE and FDE. This is due to the fact that the RNN-based architectures take into account the whole trajectory in contrast to the static methods, which can only model the data within the input window. Also, LSTM and GRU are able to employ large trajectories efficiently, without overfitting on the training data, or suffering from the vanishing and the exploding gradient issues. On the other hand, the static methods are unsuited for too long-term dependencies. For instance, MLPs overfit on the training data when using too large windows.

Furthermore, the SVMr method gives the worst predictions after the linear model. However, the SVMr models were trained on a subset of the available data due to the SVM's training complexity is highly dependent on the dataset size (it is known to be at least quadratic to the number of data points). Moreover, a comparison among the tree-based algorithms predictions shows that in almost all trajectory points the best solution found by the AdaBoost outperforms the RFT, followed by CART. Also, the MLP model predicts better than the CART in terms of ADE, but the CART is more accurate than the MLP in terms of the FDE in the Aegean-Cyclades dataset. Concerning the RNN-based methods, the LSTM outperforms the GRU model.

Moreover, Figs. 2 and 3 depict, in the form of boxplots, the FDE in meters for the UTM eastings and northings coordinates separately. The conclusion drawn is that there do exist slight differences when comparing the error in the two coordinates but the general behaviour is more or less the same. Finally, it should be noted that we performed experiments by feeding the LSTM model with actual values instead of intervals for the Aegean-Cyclades dataset case. The produced FDE of the LSTM model by using actual values was about 8235m, i.e., about 4 times higher than the FDE produced by the LSTM with interval values, which justifies our choice to work on the differences rather than the actual coordinate values.

V. CONCLUSION

Due to the recent advances in position broadcasting technology and the "explosion" of vessel surveillance data, vessel

TABLE I
 PREDICTION RESULTS FOR Δt UP TO 30 MIN. AND r UP TO 6 TRANSITIONS (UNIT: METERS)

Data	Method	ADE per Δt in min. for $r=6$					FDE(30 min)	
		5	10	15	20	25		30
Aegean-Cyclades	Linear	867	1717	2569	3420	4271	5121	9371
	CART	340	889	1481	1916	2335	2796	5102
	RFT	221	654	1114	1506	1911	2377	4709
	AdaBoost	230	640	984	1374	1785	2217	4376
	SVMr	638	1335	2223	2938	3706	4310	7328
	MLP	180	735	1290	1782	2264	2765	5270
	GRU	79	195	337	511	727	977	2229
	LSTM	76	184	317	481	684	920	2097
Brest	Linear	1158	1788	2412	3030	3642	4312	7666
	CART	571	1091	1679	2218	2708	3247	5945
	RFT	286	641	1016	1445	1852	2226	4094
	AdaBoost	252	610	983	1387	1782	2159	4041
	SVMr	697	1388	2008	2668	3276	3828	6591
	MLP	677	1067	1482	1936	2403	2894	5344
	GRU	241	466	710	959	1215	1485	2832
	LSTM	239	440	663	899	1146	1408	2719

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Boxplots for the FDE (in meters), on the Aegean-Cyclades Dataset, in the testing set, the two UTM coordinates separately: a) eastings, and b) northings.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Boxplots for the FDE (in meters), on the Brest Dataset, in the testing set, for the two UTM coordinates separately: a) eastings, and b) northings.

movement information has become increasingly available. An effective VRF tool is substantial for improving the quality and the reliability of MTS services. Taking advantage of the wealth of vessel positioning data, in particular of AIS messages, this work investigates the most popular ML methods to address the VRF problem and proposes baseline methods for VRF purposes, which can be used as a reference for MTS purposes.

Moreover, insightful findings through the experimental comparison study are provided; for instance it is clear that RNN (LSTM and GRU) models can efficiently forecast the anticipated trajectory of vessel with the average error being in the order of 0.5 km (1-1.5 km) for a 15 min. (30 min., respectively) forecast horizon.

Future work includes the investigation of weather information and nearby traffic impact on the VRF problem. Also, we plan to focus on a longer prediction time horizon (more than 30 min.). Last but not least, and taking into account the large population of today's AIS monitored fleet, we aim to research on VRF methods based on incremental learning and distributed learning strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by EU Horizon 2020 R&I Programme under Grant Agreement No 957237 (project VesselAI, <https://vessel-ai.eu>), and EU Horizon 2020 R&I Programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No 777695 (project MASTER, <http://www.master-project-h2020.eu>).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Artakis and D. Zissis, *Guide to Maritime Informatics*. Springer, 2021.
- [2] H. Georgiou, P. Petrou, P. Tampakis, S. Sideridis, E. Chondrodima, N. Pelekis, and Y. Theodoridis, "Future location and trajectory prediction," in *Big Data Analytics for Time-Critical Mobility Forecasting: From Raw Data to Trajectory-Oriented Mobility Analytics in the Aviation and Maritime Domains*. Cham: Springer, 2020, pp. 215–254.
- [3] P. Tampakis, E. Chondrodima, A. Pikrakis, Y. Theodoridis, K. Pristouris, H. Nakos, E. Petra, T. Dalamagas, A. Kandiros, G. Markakis, I. Maina, and S. Kavadas, "Sea area monitoring and analysis of fishing vessels activity: The i4sea big data platform," in *21st IEEE Int. Conf. MDM*, 2020, pp. 275–280.
- [4] P. Tampakis, E. Chondrodima, A. Tritsarolis, A. Pikrakis, Y. Theodoridis, K. Pristouris, H. Nakos, P. Kalampokis, and T. Dalamagas, "i4sea: a big data platform for sea area monitoring and analysis of fishing vessels activity," *Geo Spat. Inf. Sci.*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10095020.2021.1971055>
- [5] E. Tu, G. Zhang, L. Rachmawati, E. Rajabally, and G.-B. Huang, "Exploiting ais data for intelligent maritime navigation: A comprehensive survey from data to methodology," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 1559–1582, 2018.
- [6] D. Zissis, E. K. Xidias, and D. Lekkas, "Real-time vessel behavior prediction," *Evolving Systems*, vol. 7, pp. 29–40, 2016.
- [7] N. Zorbas, D. Zissis, K. Tserpes, and D. Anagnostopoulos, "Predicting object trajectories from high-speed streaming data," in *2015 IEEE Trustcom/BigDataSE/ISPA*, vol. 2. IEEE, 2015, pp. 229–234.
- [8] A. Valsamis, K. Tserpes, D. Zissis, D. Anagnostopoulos, and T. Varvarigou, "Employing traditional machine learning algorithms for big data streams analysis: The case of object trajectory prediction," *J. Syst. Softw.*, vol. 127, pp. 249 – 257, 2017.
- [9] S. Wang, J. Cao, and P. Yu, "Deep learning for spatio-temporal data mining: A survey," *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, 2020.
- [10] S. Capobianco, L. M. Millefiori, N. Forti, P. Braca, and P. Willett, "Deep learning methods for vessel trajectory prediction based on recurrent neural networks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.02486*, 2021.
- [11] Y. Suo, W. Chen, C. Claramunt, and S. Yang, "A ship trajectory prediction framework based on a recurrent neural network," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 18, 2020.
- [12] Y. Wang, D. Zhang, Y. Liu, and K. Tan, "Trajectory forecasting with neural networks: An empirical evaluation and a new hybrid model," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 4400–4409, 2020.
- [13] R. Trasarti, R. Guidotti, A. Monreale, and F. Giannotti, "Myway: Location prediction via mobility profiling," *Inf. Syst.*, vol. 64, pp. 350–367, 2017.
- [14] P. Petrou, P. Nikitopoulos, P. Tampakis, A. Glenis, N. Koutroumanis, G. M. Santipantakis, K. Patroumpas, A. Vlachou, H. V. Georgiou, E. Chondrodima, C. Doukeridis, N. Pelekis, G. L. Andrienko, F. Patterson, G. Fuchs, Y. Theodoridis, and G. A. Vouros, "ARGO: A big data framework for online trajectory prediction," in *16th Int. Symp. SSTD*, 2019, pp. 194–197.
- [15] H. Georgiou, N. Pelekis, S. Sideridis, D. Scarlatti, and Y. Theodoridis, "Semantic-aware aircraft trajectory prediction using flight plans," *Int. J. Data Sci. Anal.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 215–228, 2020.
- [16] P. B. Weerakody, K. W. Wong, G. Wang, and W. Ela, "A review of irregular time series data handling with gated recurrent neural networks," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 441, pp. 161–178, 2021.
- [17] D. Neil, M. Pfeiffer, and S.-C. Liu, "Phased lstm: Accelerating recurrent network training for long or event-based sequences," in *Proc. NIPS*, 2016, p. 3889–3897.
- [18] Z. Xiao, X. Fu, L. Zhang, and R. S. M. Goh, "Traffic pattern mining and forecasting technologies in maritime traffic service networks: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1796–1825, 2020.
- [19] N. Pelekis, P. Tampakis, M. Vodas, C. Panagiotakis, and Y. Theodoridis, "In-dbms sampling-based sub-trajectory clustering," in *20th Int. Conf. EDBT*, 2017, pp. 632–643.
- [20] G. Pallotta, S. Horn, P. Braca, and K. Bryan, "Context-enhanced vessel prediction based on ornstein-uhlenbeck processes using historical ais traffic patterns: Real-world experimental results," in *Int. Conf. Inf. Fusion*, 2014, pp. 1–7.
- [21] G. Pallotta, M. Vespe, and K. Bryan, "Vessel pattern knowledge discovery from ais data: A framework for anomaly detection and route prediction," *Entropy*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 2218–2245, 2013.
- [22] D. Rumelhart, G. Hinton, and R. Williams, "Learning representations by back-propagating errors," *Nature*, vol. 323, pp. 533–536, 1986.
- [23] T. G. Dietterich, "Machine learning for sequential data: A review," in *Structural, Syntactic, and Statistical Pattern Recognition*, T. Caelli, A. Amin, R. P. W. Duin, D. de Ridder, and M. Kamel, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2002, pp. 15–30.
- [24] D. Montgomery and G. Runger, *Applied Statistics and Probability for Engineers (7th/Ed.)*. John Wiley & Sons, 2018.
- [25] J. Cervantes, F. Garcia-Lamont, L. Rodriguez-Mazahua, and A. Lopez, "A comprehensive survey on support vector machine classification: Applications, challenges and trends," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 408, pp. 189–215, May 2020.
- [26] V. Vapnik, *The nature of statistical learning theory*. Springer science & business media, 2013.
- [27] C. Cortes and V. Vapnik, "Support-vector networks," *Machine learning*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 273–297, 1995.
- [28] S. Theodoridis and K. Koutroumbas, *Pattern Recognition*, 4th ed. Academic Press, November 2008.
- [29] A. Ali, "Ensemble learning model for prediction of natural gas spot price based on least squares boosting algorithm," in *Int. Conf. ICDABI*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [30] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system," in *22nd ACM SIGKDD*, 2016, pp. 785–794.
- [31] T. K. Ho, "Random decision forests," in *3rd Int. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition*, vol. 1. IEEE, 1995, pp. 278–282.
- [32] R. E. Schapire, "Explaining adaboost," in *Empirical inference*. Springer, 2013, pp. 37–52.
- [33] S. Haykin, *Neural Networks: A Comprehensive Foundation*, 2nd ed. USA: Prentice Hall PTR, 1998.
- [34] A. Poznyak, W. Yu, E. Sanchez, and J. Perez, "Nonlinear adaptive trajectory tracking using dynamic neural networks," *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1402–1411, 1999.
- [35] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long short-term memory," *Neural Comput.*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.

- [36] K. Cho, B. van Merriënboer, C. Gulcehre, D. Bahdanau, F. Bougares, H. Schwenk, and Y. Bengio, "Learning phrase representations using RNN encoder–decoder for statistical machine translation," in *Conf. EMNLP*, Oct. 2014, pp. 1724–1734.
- [37] P. J. Werbos, "Backpropagation through time: what it does and how to do it," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 78, no. 10, pp. 1550–1560, 1990.
- [38] P. D. Kingma and J. Ba, "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization," in *Int. Conf. ICLR*, 2015.
- [39] M. Veres and M. Moussa, "Deep learning for intelligent transportation systems: A survey of emerging trends," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 3152–3168, 2019.
- [40] S. Malakar, S. Goswami, B. Ganguli, A. Chakrabarti, S. S. Roy, K. Boopathi, and A. Rangaraj, "A novel feature representation for prediction of global horizontal irradiance using a bidirectional model," *Mach. Learn. Knowl. Extr.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 946–965, 2021.
- [41] K. Udeh, D. W. Wanik, N. Bassill, and E. Anagnostou, "Time series modeling of storm outages with weather mesonet data for emergency preparedness and response," in *10th IEEE Conf UEMCON*, 2019, pp. 0499–0505.
- [42] A. Graves and J. Schmidhuber, "Framewise phoneme classification with bidirectional lstm and other neural network architectures," *Neural Netw.*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 602 – 610, 2005.
- [43] C. Ray, R. Dréo, E. Camossi, A.-L. Joussetme, and C. Iphar, "Heterogeneous integrated dataset for maritime intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance," *Data in Brief*, vol. 25, p. 104141, 2019.
- [44] G. Parsons, J. Youden, and C. Fowler, "Satellite automatic identification system (sais) performance modelling and simulation," *Defence R&D Canada-Ottawa*, 2013.
- [45] A. Alexandridis, E. Chondrodima, and H. Sarimveis, "Radial basis function network training using a nonsymmetric partition of the input space and particle swarm optimization," *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 219–230, 2013.
- [46] L. Prechelt, *Early Stopping - But When?* Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1998, pp. 55–69.
- [47] A. Alexandridis, E. Chondrodima, and H. Sarimveis, "Cooperative learning for radial basis function networks using particle swarm optimization," *Appl. Soft Comput.*, vol. 49, pp. 485 – 497, 2016.
- [48] D.-w. Gao, Y.-s. Zhu, J.-f. Zhang, Y.-k. He, K. Yan, and B.-r. Yan, "A novel mp-lstm method for ship trajectory prediction based on ais data," *Ocean Eng.*, vol. 228, p. 108956, 2021.
- [49] B. Zhang, Z. Xu, J. Zhang, and G. Wu, "A warning framework for avoiding vessel-bridge and vessel-vessel collisions based on generative adversarial and dual-task networks," *Comput.-Aided Civ. Infrastruct. Eng.*, 2021.